

Implementation strategy of primary health care in Ovia communities

Osarenmwanta Aideyan Daniel¹, Timothy A. Akingbade², Mohamed Nor Azhari Azman³,
Jems K.R. Maay⁴

^{1,2}Department of Health, Safety and Environmental Education, Faculty of Education, University of Benin, Nigeria

³Faculty of Technical and Vocational, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, Malaysia

⁴Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health Jayapura, Jayapura City, Papua, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 23, 2021

Revised May 14, 2021

Accepted Jun 16, 2021

Keywords:

Community health
Health promotion
Primary health care
Rural based strategies

ABSTRACT

Primary health care is the essential health service provided at the grassroot level. Over the years the implementation of Primary Health Care (PHC) programmes in Edo state are bedeviled with associated challenges such as limited community participation, great communication gap that limit evaluation processes of PHC programme and slow pace collaboration among stakeholders. These challenges need to be averted through effective and people oriented strategies to ensure the implementation of primary health care. A descriptive research design with a population of the study comprised 1,024 primary health care stakeholders in Edo state. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 180 respondents for the study. The study found that intersectoral collaboration involving partnerships with community health agencies such as village health committees and ward health committees significantly influenced the implementation of PHC. Intersectoral collaboration, community mobilization strategy and community feedback mechanism are effective and efficient strategies for improved implementation of PHC programmes. The study recommended among others that National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA) and State Primary Health Care Development Agency (SPHCDA) should strengthen partnership with international health organizations such as WHO, UNICEF, GAVI, UNDP and boost confidence and trust of these international organizations.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Mohamed Nor Azhari Azman
Faculty of Technical and Vocational
Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris
35900 Tanjong Malim, Perak, Malaysia
Email: mnazhari@ftv.upsi.edu.my

1. INTRODUCTION

The provision of health services that is accessible, culturally acceptable and affordable to all in the community can be achieved through primary health care (PHC). The World Health Organization (WHO) describes primary care as essential health care based on practical, scientifically sound, and socially acceptable methods and technology made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community by means acceptable to them and at a cost that the community and the country can afford to maintain at every stage of their development in a spirit of self-reliance and self-determination [1]. It is the first level of contact for individuals, the family, and the community with the national health system, bringing health care as close as possible to where people live and work, and this constitutes the first element of a continuing healthcare

process. Primary health care is the essential health service provided at the grassroots level that is accessible, culturally accepted, technologically driven with maximum coverage level to ensure health for all that is equally affordable at every stage of the community development [2]. Despite this central role, PHC services are still inefficient and still lack full coverage in relation to accessibility, affordability and acceptability and presently lacking the needed technologies to promote efficiency and coverage in Nigeria [3]. These ascertained challenges are obviously from literatures affecting the implementation of primary health care and possibly unfocused and poor result oriented strategies used over the years to curtail the challenges [4].

Primary health care as part of Nigerian health care system is not devoid of challenges related to accessibility, cultural acceptability and responsiveness within adequate financing details, planning and management [5]. The challenges facing primary health care services have raised death rate, infant mortality rate, maternal mortality rate, and child mortality rate, increased prevalent rate of chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, stroke, hypertension and also lower life expectancy of the people in Nigeria [6]. These challenges need to be averted through effective and people oriented strategies to ensure effective and efficient implementation of primary health care.

The major health indicators of any country as set by WHO include neonatal mortality rate, post-natal mortality rate, infant mortality rate, and maternal mortality rate and coverage level of immunization [7]. It is dissatisfying that Nigeria in general and Edo state specifically still records high in these health indicators. This is as a result of recurring community-based challenges facing the implementation of PHC services in Nigeria [8]. These challenges include from the poor political will of government to implement the guidelines and standard set up by WHO in rendering health services at the grass root level and lack of drugs to dispense to sick individuals. It is sometimes difficult to access the clinic due to bad road network; poor community participation, underfunding of community health programmes, corruption, and poor commitment of health workers equally affects the implementation of PHC. Eneanya [9] reported in a study carried out in Ondo state, Nigeria that the level of supervisory activities is low; hence, the ad-hoc staff often times do not carry out what is expected of them in the field during immunization as cultural beliefs conflict with the acceptance and utilization of PHC services.

Primary health care being a community activity and programme, requires strategies or initiatives that are community based and collaborative in nature with interest towards community mobilization, intersectoral partnership and periodic health communication network [10], [11]. It is reported that many developing countries like Nigeria could not attain the global health for all by the year 2000 because initiatives were not community based; rather they are sociopolitical in nature such as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS). Current interest in the revitalization of primary health care makes it more acceptable, effective and efficient utilizing advocacy for strong community mobilization and regular evaluation of the programmes of PHC [12].

The debate about PHC strategies has intensified over decades and measures to strengthen primary health care are integral part of the reorganization and implementation of PHC in Nigeria. ESMOH [13] and Abimbola [14] explained that strategies for improved implementation of PHC in Nigeria should have six directions: Work with the local communities; identify and remove health inequalities; offer access to comprehensive health services to improve, maintain and restore people's health; coordinate health care across service areas; develop primary health care workforce; and continuously improve quality using good and reliable information. Intersectoral collaboration strategy is an approach of bringing together stakeholders of health within and outside the country to intensify efforts towards providing health services and improved implementation of primary health care [15]. It could include health professional groups, international health agencies, communities, ministries in the state government and financial donor's holis. Obansa and Orimisan [16] reported that partnership with private sectors, NGOs, communities and development partners as well as other social and economic sector is essential to deliver PHC that can meet the needs of the population on a sustainable basis. Community mobilization approach support implementation of PHC by empowering community members and groups such as ward health committees, women group health committees to take action to facilitate necessary change towards accessibility, acceptability and efficiency of primary health care. The implementation of primary health care requires community based strategy of collaborating with community members to plan, implement and evaluate primary health care programmes. It was stated by Abosede and Sholeye [17] that engaging diverse health organizations, community leaders and community members will raise spirit of ownership and promotes participation in the need assessment, shared decision making to support and improve on sense of commitment and ownership of the vision and plan of PHC.

The performance of primary health care cannot be left to chance. Feedback mechanism strategy using agreed indicators helps to determine the relevance, utilization, achievement, effectiveness and efficiency of PHC programmes and policies. Feedback mechanism strategy is a form of monitoring and evaluation procedures and [18] expressed that effective feedback mechanism through effective monitoring and evaluation procedures improves achievements and implementation of PHC goals and objectives.

Roalkvam and Jani [19] listed the following as merits of feedback mechanism in PHC; selecting health needs from the people's perspectives, mobilizing local resources for PHC, enhancing commitment to achieving collective objectives, enhancing transparency, accountability, efficiency and success of primary health care, enhancing accuracy and reliability of information and building capacity for PHC programmes sustainability. Finally, the poor health status of the people of Edo state could be as a result of poor, inefficient strategies that affect the effective implementation of PHC, It is against this background the researcher wants to analyze rural based strategies in the implementation of primary health care in Ovia communities, Edo state [20].

Health programmes, health policies and activities have been carried out to ensure effective health services delivery in order to raise the standard of living of the people, reduce mortality rate from preventable diseases and increase life expectancy of the people in Nigeria and Edo state specifically. However, the observations from the researcher's in some selected PHC centres in Edo state and the national health statistics provide high estimates of infant mortality rate, maternal mortality rate, high still-birth rate, malnutrition, prevalence of childhood diseases like poliomyelitis, measles, tetanus and diphtheria especially in rural areas of Edo state. In many of the South-South states like Edo, Delta, Bayelsa and Cross Rivers, reports of inadequate number of trained health providers, health inequality, insufficient funding, superstitious belief, and lack of community participation, inadequate facilities and poor coordination have been reported over the years and interventions have been directed to these enlisted challenges [21].

Also, the neglect of community approaches to improve implementation of PHC in the Edo state is worthy of concern as strategy such as improved financing has not significantly improved the implementation of PHC in South-South states [22], [23]. Again, there is lack of utilization of community based strategies that are needed to improve the implementation of primary health care in order to meet the objectives of primary health care services to the people in communities. It is against this background that the researcher assessed the rural-based strategies in the implementation of primary health care in Edo state.

The following research hypotheses formulated were tested for the study;

- Intersectoral collaboration in the community will not significantly influence the implementation of primary health care in Ovia communities, Edo state.
- Community mobilization strategy will not significantly influence the implementation of primary health care Ovia communities, Edo state.
- Community feedback mechanism will not significantly influence the implementation of primary health care Ovia communities, Edo state.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The study employed the descriptive research design of survey method. It is called descriptive research design because the information about the independent and dependent variables that are gathered represent the current trend at a particular point in time [24], [25]. The population of the study comprised all PHC providers in Edo state. The target population for this study includes State PHC staff, Local Government PHC staff, Ward PHC staff and other PHC service providers in Edo state which totaled 1,024 [12]. The sample for the study was 180. The multi-stage sampling technique was used for the sampling approach. In the first stage, cluster sampling technique was used to select three senatorial districts; Edo north, Edo south and Edo central. Secondly, in each of the senatorial district, three LGAs were selected. Finally, the researchers then purposively selected 20 PHC stakeholders from the PHC centers in each of the LGAs selected. Therefore, 20 PHC stakeholders selected from the 9 LGAs totaled 180. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: Sections A and B. Section A elicited information on the socio-demographic data like age, gender, occupation and marital status among others. Section B consisted of questions that obtained information about the variables formulated in the hypotheses. The questionnaire was a closed-ended of four-options Likert rating scale where the respondents were asked to tick (√) one out of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was content validated by three experts in public health and health education. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, the researcher used the test re-test method of reliability. The questionnaires were pilot tested among 18 PHC stakeholders. The questionnaires were re-administered after two weeks interval. The data collected from the two administrations were subjected to the statistic of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and a reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained. The instrument was administered by the researcher with the aid of three trained research assistants who were indigenes of the sampled areas. The inferential statistic of Chi-square was used to test the null hypotheses formulated at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

3. RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: Intersectoral collaboration in the community will not significantly influence the implementation of primary health care in Ovia communities, Edo state.

The Table 1 presents the Chi-square analysis of the formulated hypothesis. The table revealed that the calculated chi-square value of 129.72 was greater than the critical value of 16.92 with degree of freedom 9, at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the formulated null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that intersectoral collaboration strategy significantly influenced the implementation of PHC programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state.

Table 1. Chi-square analysis showing stakeholders responses on intersectoral collaboration strategy and implementation of PHC programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state, Nigeria

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Row Total	Df	Cal χ^2	Critical value	Decision
Working with organizations outside Nigeria can promote better PHC.	115(64%)	61(34%)	2(1%)	2(1%)	180				
Partnership with other ministries in Nigeria will enhance better PHC.	115(64%)	58(32%)	4(2%)	3(2%)	180				
Partnership with NGOs will enhance communities' members' acceptance on PHC.	115(64%)	63(35%)	1(1%)	1(1%)	180	9	129.72	16.92	Ho Rejected
Bringing other PHC stakeholders will enhance supervision of PHC programmes.	110(61%)	54(30%)	8(4%)	8(4%)	180				
	Column Total	455(63%)	236(33%)	15(2%)	14(2%)	720			

p=0.05

Hypothesis 2: Community mobilization strategy will not significantly influence the implementation of primary health care in Ovia communities, Edo state.

The Table 2 presented the chi-square analysis of the formulated hypothesis above. The table revealed that the calculated chi-square value of 138.44 was greater than the critical value of 16.92 with degree of freedom 9, at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the formulated null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that community mobilization strategy significantly influenced the implementation of PHC programmes in Edo state.

Table 2. Chi-square analysis showing stakeholders' responses on community mobilization strategy and implementation of PHC programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state, Nigeria

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Row Total	Df	Cal χ^2	Critical value	Decision
Community mobilization increases the utilization of PHC services	120(45.8%)	50(27.7%)	10(5.5%)	10(5.5%)	180				
Bringing communities members together raises the spirit of ownership of PHC facilities.	112(62.2%)	60(33.3%)	4(2.2%)	4(2.2%)	180				
Community mobilization strategy raises stakeholders' consciousness of their roles and responsibilities towards PHC implementation.	100(55.6%)	50(27.8%)	15(8.3%)	15(8.3%)	180	9	138.44	16.92	Ho Rejected
Community mobilization strategy empower communities to mobilize resources for PHC implementation.	80(44.4%)	82(45.6%)	10(5.6%)	8(4.4%)	180				

p=0.05

Hypothesis 3: Community feedback mechanism will not significantly influence the implementation of primary health care Ovia communities, Edo state.

The Table 3 presented the chi-square analysis of the formulated hypothesis above. The table revealed that the calculated chi-square value of 133.17 was greater than the critical value of 16.92 with

degree of freedom 9, at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the formulated null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that community feedback mechanism significantly influenced the implementation of PHC programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state.

Table 3. Chi-square analysis showing stakeholders' responses on community mobilization strategy and implementation of PHC programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Row total	Df	Cal χ^2	Critical value	Decision
Feedback mechanism strategy promotes community participation in PHC.	110(61%)	54(30%)	8(4%)	8(4%)	180				
Feedback mechanism strategy ensures PHC stakeholders are committed to the objectives of PHC.	112(68%)	58(32%)	5(3%)	5(3%)	180				
Feedback mechanism strategy addresses the problems that can arise during planning and implementation of PHC.	136(76%)	40(22%)	2(1%)	2(1%)	180	9	133.17	16.92	Ho Rejected
Feedback mechanism strategy helps PHC stakeholders to achieve the objectives of PHC.	110(61%)	50(28%)	12(7%)	8(4%)	180				
	Column Total	1789	1614	225	208	5754			

p=0.05

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that the result of hypothesis 6 revealed that intersectoral collaboration strategy significantly influenced the implementation of primary health services programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state. The PHC stakeholders agreed that partnership with other ministries other than ministry of health can promote better PHC. They further agreed that collaboration with non-governmental organizations such as WHO, UNICEF, UNDP, GAVI and UNEP can promote the effectiveness and efficiency of PHC implementation. The finding above corroborated with that of El Arifeen [26], [27] which reported that partnership with private sectors, NGOs, communities, other related ministries and developmental partners was essential to delivered PHC services that can meet the health needs of the people in communities. In fact, NPHCD [5] reported that intersectoral collaboration strategy intensified commitment on part of government and PHC service providers promote funding and help to realize the objectives of PHC. In a similar vein, Bloch [28], [29] affirmed that for a holistic approach to sustainable implementation of PHC, intersectoral collaboration strategy was important and must be adopted as a valuable key principle to achieved effective and efficient implementation of PHC in communities.

The study also revealed that community mobilization strategy significantly influenced the effective implementation of primary health services programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state. The PHC stakeholders agreed that community mobilization strategy increased the utilization of PHC, raised the spirit of ownership among community members and help to mobilized resources for the implementation of PHC. The finding above corroborated with the finding of Abosede and Sholeye [17] that through community mobilization strategy, diverse health organizations, community leaders and community members engaged in the planning and management of PHC, raised spirit of ownership and promote participation in the identification and assessment of the health needs of the communities. Also, Brown and Schafft [30], [6] reported that community mobilization strategy improved stakeholders' participation, improved resources mobilization, allowed for flow of information, ensured effective health needs identification and improved the health and quality of life of the people in the communities through the effective implementation of PHC in communities.

The study revealed that community feedback mechanism significantly influenced the implementation of primary health services programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state. The PHC service providers indicated that community feedback mechanism ensures PHC stakeholders are committed to the objectives of PHC, addressed the problems that arise during the planning and implementation of PHC and provided better communication links between health care providers and community members. The finding corroborated with the finding of Kweku [31]-[33] that community feedback mechanism ensured improved PHC stakeholders' commitment, addressed problems during the planning and management of PHC programmes, provided for accountability and efficiency of health services.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that intersectoral collaboration strategy influenced the implementation of primary health care programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state. Community mobilization strategy influenced the implementation of primary health care programmes in Ovia communities, Edo state, as bringing together diverse health organization, community leaders and community members engaged all in promoting community participation and health needs assessment of the communities. Community feedback mechanism influenced the implementation of primary health care in Ovia communities, Edo state as it improves primary health care stakeholders' commitment, address problems that could arise during planning and management of primary health care implementation, close communication gap and help to evaluate the achievements of the goals and objectives of primary health care implementation. Thus, State Primary Health Care Development Agency (SPHCDA) should fast track the development of functional village health committees that will ensure community participation and other health outreaches to promote PHC implementation. State government should incorporate related ministries such as ministries of information, education, finance and environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Du S. *et al.*, "The knowledge, ability, and skills of primary health care providers in SEANERN countries: a multi-national cross-sectional study," *BMC Health Serv Res*, vol. 19, no. 602, pp 1-8, 2019.
- [2] Starfield B., "Politics, primary healthcare and health," *Journal of Epidemiol Community Health*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 653-655, 2011.
- [3] Oyibocho E. O, Irinoye O, Sagua E.O, Ogungide-Essien O.T, Edeki J. E, and Okome O. L., "Sustainable health care system in Nigeria Vision, strategies and challenges," *Journal of Economics and Finance*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 28-39, 2014.
- [4] Martin M., "The implementation of school-based management in public elementary schools," *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 44-56, 2019.
- [5] Welcome M. O., "The Nigerian health care system: Need for integrating adequate medical intelligence and surveillance systems." *Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 470-478, 2011
- [6] Efe S. I., "Health care problems and management in Nigeria," *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 244-254, 2013.
- [7] Adeniyi J. O., Oladepo A., and Soyibo O. O., "Survey of primary health care services delivery in Lagos and Kogi. A field report," *Journal of African Regional Health Education*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 79-87, 2013.
- [8] Alagbonsi L.A, Afolabi A.O, Bamidele O, and Aliyu O.F, "Causes and management of poor health care services delivery in Kwara state, Nigeria: Students' perception," *American Journal of Research Communication*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 126-133, 2013.
- [9] Eneanya A. N., "Linking Primary Healthcare Policies with Health System for Improved Health Outcomes in Nigeria: Issues, Controversies, Problems, and Solutions," *In Human Rights, Public Values, and Leadership in Healthcare Policy*, 2019, pp. 87-114, IGI Global, doi:10.4018/978-1-5225-6133-0.ch005.
- [10] Leenaars K. E. F., Smit E., Wagemakers A., Molleman G. R. M., and Koelen M. A., "Facilitators and barriers in the collaboration between the primary care and the sport sector in order to promote physical activity: a systematic literature review," *Preventive Medicine*, vol. 81, pp. 460-478, 2015.
- [11] Greenhalgh T., Jackson C., Shaw S., and Janamian T., "Achieving research impact through co-creation in community-based health services: literature review and case study," *The Milbank Quarterly*, vol. 94, no. 2, pp. 392-429, 2016.
- [12] Assefa Y., Gelaw Y. A., Hill P. S., Taye B. W., and Van Damme W., "Community health extension program of Ethiopia, 2003–2018: successes and challenges toward universal coverage for primary healthcare services," *Globalization and Health*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 1-11, 2019.
- [13] Edo State Ministry of Health (ESMOH), "Edo State Ministry of Health 2010-2020 Strategic Plan," Benin City. ESMOH Publications, 2015. [Online]. Available: https://ewdata.rightsindevelopment.org/files/documents/80/WB-P151480_vBjTuzn.pdf
- [14] Abimbola S., "How to improve the quality of primary health care in Nigeria. Abuja. NPHCDA Publications, 2012.
- [15] Heshka L., McPhee L., and Wollbaum M., "Leading collaboration among the providers of primary health care," Geneva: WHO Publications, 2011.
- [16] Obansa S. A. J. and Orimisan A., "Health care financing in Nigeria: prospects and challenges," *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp 221-221, 2013.
- [17] Aboosedo O. A. and Sholeye O. F., "Strengthening the foundation for sustainable primary health care services in Nigeria," *Journal of Primary Health Care*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 167-175, 2014.
- [18] Abdurraheem B. I., Oladipo A. R., and Amodu M. O., "Primary Health Care Services in Nigeria: Crical Issues and strategies for enhancing the use by the rural communities, 2012. Available at: <http://uilspace.unilorin.edu.ng:8081/jspui/handle/123456789/344>
- [19] Roalkvam S. and Jani J., "Rights and obligations in national health governance." Protecting the World's Children: Immunisation policies and Practices, 2013.

- [20] Osuyi S. O. and Eboh P. A., "Analysis of the relevance of basic electricity to Home Economics Students in Technical Colleges in Edo State, Nigeria," *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 27-33, 2020, doi: 10.37134/ajatel.vol10.2.4.2020.
- [21] Donbraye E., Adewumi M. O., Odaibo G. N., Bakarey A.S., and Opaleye O. O., "Evaluation of immunity against poliovirus serotypes among children in riverine areas of Delta State, Nigeria," *African Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 72-75, 2011.
- [22] Waziri H. I., "Community Ownership of Micro Projects and Sustainability of Poverty Reduction Projects in Yobe State, Nigeria," *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 44-62, 2018.
- [23] Udalla E. A. and Ezegwu C., "Contradictory Projection of Development in the South-South States of Nigeria: Implications for Scaling Up and Sustaining Development," 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1905217>
- [24] Wilford G., "Doing qualitative educational research: A personal guide to the research process," London: Continuum, 2015.
- [25] Reeves S., Peller J., Goldman J., and Kitto S., "Ethnography in qualitative educational research: AMEE Guide No. 80," *Medical Teacher*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. e1365-e1379, 2013, doi: 10.3109/0142159X.2013.804977.
- [26] El. Arifeen S. *et al.*, "Community-based approaches and partnerships: innovations in health-service delivery in Bangladesh," *The Lancet*, vol. 382, no. 9909, pp. 2012-2026, 2013, doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62149-2.
- [27] Story W. T. *et al.*, "Institutionalizing community-focused maternal, newborn, and child health strategies to strengthen health systems: a new framework for the sustainable development goal era," *Globalization and Health*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1-13, 2017.
- [28] Bloch P. *et al.*, "Revitalizing the setting approach—supersettings for sustainable impact in community health promotion," *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1-15, 2014.
- [29] Onokerhoraye A. G., "Achieving universal access to health care in Africa: The role of primary health care," *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 9-31, 2016.
- [30] Brown D. L. and Schafft K. A., "Rural people and communities in the 21st century: Resilience and transformation," Polity, 2011.
- [31] Kweku M. *et al.*, "Community-based health planning and services plus programme in Ghana: a qualitative study with stakeholders in two systems learning districts on improving the implementation of primary health care," *PLoS One*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0226808.
- [32] Naledi T., Barron P., and Schneider H., "Primary health care in SA since 1994 and implications of the new vision for PHC re-engineering," *South African Health Review*, vol. 2011, no. 1, pp. 17-28, 2011.
- [33] Schneider H., English R., Tabana H., Padayachee T., and Orgill M., "Whole-system change: case study of factors facilitating early implementation of a primary health care reform in a South African province," *BMC Health Services Research*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1-11, 2014.